

COVID-19 Impacting on Mental Health on the Healthcare Workers in Pakistan

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Abstract:

This research investigates the COVID-19 impacting on Mental health on the health workers in Pakistan. The study is based on desktop and data is congregated via secondary sources including Government's official websites to update latest information on pandemic of COVID-19. Furthermore, the results are discussed using the same research papers produced to emphasise the community services and social activists' important position in the situation in Pakistan. The methodology of research itself defines the aim of entire strategy which will be executed in the research paper. The parts of methodology of research conducted on coronavirus disease are as under: The research is investigative in nature and the research is done on the surveying basis, including both primary and secondary sources and containing surveys to further conduct surveys throughout the research. It was revealed that most of the healthcare people are more depressed, families were suffered from COVID-19 and load of burden in working in different parts. Government is not supporting co-health workers.

Key Words: COVID-19, Mental Health, Healthcare, Pakistan

Introduction: During pandemic of COVID-19 the other main issue raised and took place is Domestic violence which has strongly affected the vulnerable population whereas Domestic violence is defined as abusing behaviour to the one person with another in specifically concubinage or married life. It is usually done in between partners who have been ex or currently spouses living together also in between same gender or heterosexual relationships. The other severe infringement is against older parents with no other income except their children. In most cases, COVID-19 mental health problems harm the wives of their children. Domestic Violation is the serious concern needed to be addressed which is in various forms including sex, reproduction, religious, emotional, physical, verbal, economical and so on abuses which has also the great impact on quality life.(Kenney, 2011). There are no any pre decided parameters who can be affected by domestic violence despite of age race gender. Violation can be in both terms whether physical or psychological violation, the major vulnerable population are those harmful sufferers including adults and young adults and that strongly needed to be addressed and reduce the risk of mental illness due to domestic violation. The people working in healthcare sector in Pakistan are on high risk to develop COVID-19 rather than any of other sector in this pandemic which ultimately results the possible unfavourable mental health consequences during this outbreak of COVID-19. The possible reasons of more risk in healthcare workers to develop COVID-19 are insignificant quantity of PPEs, possible chances of getting infected from the COVID carrier patient, longer hours of working to serve ill community due to COVID-19, physical lethargy due to extraordinary efforts than regular, loneliness in this pandemic, detachment from Families and loved ones.

Risks of mental health issues related to COVID-19 in unsafe populations

So far Seven publications have deeply identified the specific unsafe populations who are at high risk of mental health issues regarding the impact of COVID-19 pandemic, some of these have suggested for intervention & service providing. Also Chinese students are studying overseas, the unsafe groups of populations identified by several authors mentioned below:

- Older adults
- The homeless

- Migrant workers
- The mentally ill
- Pregnant women

During the COVID-19 period it is important for psychiatrist to be accustomed to testing and sorting and to work in close cooperation with other health practitioners, like doctors and experts on public health, to minimise their risk. Considering other populations mentioned above with specific issues raised including the high ratio of pre standing depressive sign and symptoms specifically in the elderly patients and the lack of accessing to mental health services, the people have also the fear of involuntary admission due to coronavirus disease or quarantine among the homeless populations which may be a greater barrier to mental wellbeing and may arise as a mental health issues. The need of awareness and social support among populations who are considered as migrant workers to minimise the risk of usual mental disorders.

Research Methodology

Data were collected from both primary and secondary sources and containing surveys to further conduct surveys throughout the research. This can be considered as one of core ingredient while research designing, this research consists of non-probability sampling technique and been used as deposited sampling to gather data from the targeted audience across Pakistan. Aim of this research is to identify the ongoing healthcare system of Pakistan during pandemic of COVID-19, data was collected during ongoing survey process. In this research study on Impact of COVID-19 on Healthcare system in Pakistan is based on two variables one of them is Dependant and other one is Independent, as per research Healthcare system in Pakistan is independent variable whereas COVID-19 is Dependent variable.

Results

The relationship between stress and anxiety related to COVID-19 and possible outcomes of maternal or neonatal outcomes. More likely unfairness and disapproval faced by Chinese students who were overseas during the time of pandemic disease of COVID-19, may lead to either anxiety or stress related disorders. All above discussed cases cooperation between Psychiatrists and other healthcare specialists from other departments of Medicine, as well as with local helping authorities to minimise the risk of COVID-19 and health workers who are working as frontline warriors is necessary to cope up the situation as soon as possible.

Hospitals in Pakistan for COVID-19

The government of Pakistan is taking numerous actions to combat the spread of the virus by the COVID in order to facilitate its communities. In this outbreak many hospitals are committed to reviving the dangerous COVID-19 pandemic in Pakistan.

There was only one hospital in Islamabad that worked. While there are seven hospitals for COVID 19 in the KPK, ten hospitals in Baluchistan are in operation, six in Punjab, four in Gilgit Baltistan and 3 in Azad Kashmir.

Designated hospitals

Specific health-care facilities have been designed to admit and manage the confirmed and suspected cases based upon convenience of quality quarantine wards at ‘Federal, Provincial and Regional level’. Each hospital and institute is anticipated to conduct availability and need assessment of materials i.e. personal protective equipment’s, lab diagnostics, and together with this the identification of means for ensuring the availability and provision of PPE’s and other necessity materials. Inform and train the IPC – Infection prevention and control teams at the chosen hospitals.

A proficient focal person from IPC team is selected in order to ensure the IPC practices implanted as well as embedded.

Graphical Representation

Province-wise Hospitals with the isolation wards for in response to COVID-19 across Pakistan

Province-wise Quarantine facilities in response to COVID-19 across the country

Social workers and volunteering activities

In Pakistan, the social workers and volunteer individuals are playing active role in their communities to help the poor and vulnerable groups. They have started their own charity foundations with the help of rich community members so they can at least fulfill the basic necessities of people. The teams are regularly delivering the ‘Rashan’ and ‘Preventive equipment’s i.e. gloves, face masks, sanitizers to families while maintaining social distancing

Conclusions:

The study is based on desktop and data is congregated via secondary sources including Government’s official websites to update latest information on pandemic of COVID-19. In addition, the results are analysed using the same research papers carried out with the data designed to emphasise the services of the society and the important role played by social activists in Pakistan's conditions. The methodology of research itself defines the aim of entire strategy which will be executed in the research paper.

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